

Decomposition of Propan-2-ol over Chromite Spinel—Kinetic Studies

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The decomposition of propan-2-ol has been investigated over copper, zinc and cobalt chromite catalysts in the vapour phase in a flow reactor. The decomposition of propan-2-ol to acetone follows a first order kinetics. The kinetic data obtained on zinc oxide are also included to show the better performance of the spinel compared to simple oxide. The order of reactivity for the decomposition shows the following order: cobalt chromite < zinc chromite < copper chromite. Zinc and cobalt chromites are more active when they are pretreated in oxygen than in hydrogen. Over zinc chromite the desorption of acetone is found to be the rate controlling step. However, over cobalt chromite the desorption of hydrogen is what determines the rate.

SPINELS are mixed metal oxides represented by general formula AB_2O_4 , where A and B represent bivalent (Cu, Co, Ni, Mn, Zn, Mg) and trivalent (Al, Fe, Cr) metals, respectively. Spinel is reported to be thermally stable and they maintain enhanced and sustained activity for a variety of industrially important reactions such as decomposition of nitrous oxide¹, hydrodesulphurization of petroleum crudes², oxidation and dehydrogenation of hydrocarbons^{3,4} and methanation of carbon monoxide⁵. Considering the decomposition of propan-2-ol, Kuriacose *et al.*^{6,7} have investigated this reaction over Zn:Cr:Fe and Cr_2O_3 catalysts. Copper catalyst has been used by Gryazova *et al.*⁸ for the dehydrogenation, while silver catalyst has been employed by Stadnik⁹ for the oxidation of propan-2-ol. Some of the other catalysts used for this reaction were indium oxide¹⁰, $\eta-Al_2O_3$, $\theta-Al_2O_3$, $MgAl_2O_4$ ¹¹ and alkali cation exchanged zeolites¹². In the present investigation, $CuCr_2O_4$, $ZnCr_2O_4$, $CoCr_2O_4$ and ZnO have been prepared and their catalytic activities in the kinetic decomposition of propan-2-ol to acetone have been compared, which have not so far been reported.

Experimental

Preparation of materials: The catalysts were prepared by the following methods¹³. The nitrates of the metals employed for the preparation of the catalysts were AnalaR (B.D.H.) samples and used as such. 10% solutions of the nitrates in water were prepared and they were mixed in the molar ratio M (M=Co, Zn, Cu):Cr=1:2 and the mixture was heated to 60-80°. To the hot mixture, a 5% ammonia solution was added dropwise with constant and uniform stirring. In the case of cobalt chromite the pH of the solution was maintained at 8 and in other cases it was kept at 6.5 during the precipitation. The mixture was digested for another 2 hr at the same temperature to complete precipitation. The precipitate was filtered

and dried in an air oven at 80° for 24 hr. Calcination of copper and cobalt chromites was done at 650°, while of zinc chromite at 700° for 8 hr, in an atmosphere of circulating air. Formation of spinels was checked by X-ray diffraction^{13,14}.

Propan-2-ol AnalaR (B.D.H.) was distilled before use and its purity was more than 99% by gas chromatographic analysis.

Apparatus and procedure: The reactions were carried out at atmospheric pressure in a fixed bed flow type reactor using 20-40 mesh size catalyst. The experimental procedures were the same as described earlier¹⁵.

Orsat's gas analyser was used for analysing the gaseous products. The liquid products were identified and estimated by an AIMIL dual column gas chromatograph, using an one meter column of carbowax on chromosorb.

On all the four catalysts, acetone was the main product. In addition to acetone, a small amount of 4-methyl-2-pentanone (MIBK) was obtained on copper chromite. The gaseous products consisted mainly of hydrogen with traces of propene and carbon dioxide.

Results and Discussion

From the effect of contact time, W/F (where W is weight of catalyst and F is flow rate), on the overall conversion of propan-2-ol the values of $\log(1/1-x)$ were evaluated and plotted against contact time in Fig. 1. The straight line plots indicate that the decomposition of propan-2-ol to acetone follows first order kinetics. The rate constants calculated from the slopes (slope = $k/2.303$) of these plots are presented in Table I which are also compared with the rate constants obtained from the first order equation.

The formation of acetone as a function of contact time over $CuCr_2O_4$, $ZnCr_2O_4$ and $CoCr_2O_4$

Fig. 1. First order plots.

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FROM THE SLOPES OF THE FIRST ORDER PLOTS AND FROM THE FIRST ORDER EQUATION

Temp. °C	Rate constant k (hr^{-1}) from the first order equation			
	ZnO	ZnCr ₂ O ₄	CoCr ₂ O ₄	CuCr ₂ O ₄
150				0.7498
185	0.0453			
190				0.3804
230	0.2070			0.8703
270	0.3498			1.3020
280		0.2033		
310	0.3050	0.4875	0.2035	
340	0.7055	1.0450		
345			0.2668	
370	1.6330	1.6990		
400	2.4530	2.3200		
420			0.3169	
From the slope	0.3070 (310°)	0.4880 (310°)	0.3169 (310°)	1.2500 (270°)

Fig. 1a. Arrhenius plots.

are plotted in Figs. 2-4, respectively. The rate of formation of acetone is higher at the beginning as could be seen from slopes of these curves. At higher contact time, a part of the adsorbed acetone may be oxidised to CO₂ by the lattice oxygen. This is evident from the evolution of CO₂ during the reaction. The mole percentage of CO₂ obtained for CuCr₂O₄ at contact times of 0.5, 0.9 and 1.6 hr are 1.3, 3.7 and 6.4, respectively. Evolution of CO₂ over other catalysts were negligible. The formation of CO₂ has been further confirmed by carrying

Fig. 2. Effect of contact time on the formation of acetone over CuCr₂O₄.

Fig. 3. Effect of contact time on the formation of acetone over ZnCr₂O₄.

Fig. 4. Effect of contact time on the formation of acetone over CoCr_2O_4 .

out runs with acetone alone over CuCr_2O_4 . A second factor for lower rate of formation of acetone at higher contact time may be due to the reverse reaction as reported by Kuriacose *et al*¹⁶.

Zinc and cobalt chromites, when pretreated in an atmosphere of hydrogen, showed a decrease in catalytic activity for the decomposition of propan-2-ol (Table 2). On chromite spinels the Cr(III)

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF PRETREATMENT. CONTACT TIME 0.9 hr.

Catalyst	Temp. °C	Pretreatment	Acetone (mole%)
Zinc chromite	310	oxidised	37
	310	reduced	25
	340	oxidised	68
	370	oxidised	81
Cobalt chromite	370	reduced	62
	310	oxidised	20
	310	reduced	17
	345	oxidised	33
	380	oxidised	56
	380	reduced	39

ions could be the active sites for the dehydrogenation. This view was confirmed in solid solutions of nickel-aluminium-chromium oxide¹⁷. When the catalyst is kept in an atmosphere of hydrogen the Cr(III) ions may probably be reduced to Cr(II) ions. Chromous ions may be less effective for the dehydrogenation of alcohols, though they were reported to be active in the dehydrogenation of hydrocarbons¹⁸. In addition, hydrogen may strip off several layers of lattice oxygen during reduction, which involve in the oxidative dehydrogenation of propan-2-ol. The occurrence of oxidative dehydrogenation in addition to the normal dehydrogenation has been confirmed by working out the material

balance between the amount of acetone formed and the volume of hydrogen evolved.

The activation energies in k. J/mole for the catalysts CoCr_2O_4 , ZnCr_2O_4 , CuCr_2O_4 and ZnO are 25.75, 67.63, 34.28 and 51.37, respectively. For the decomposition of propan-2-ol, CuCr_2O_4 exhibits maximum activity followed by ZnCr_2O_4 and CoCr_2O_4 , respectively. CoCr_2O_4 has the lowest activation energy and hence it may be expected to show the maximum activity. But it is found to be the least active, probably due to different active sites that are involved in the decomposition reaction.

Comparing the activity of ZnCr_2O_4 with ZnO , the latter is found less active than the former. This proves that a spinel is a better catalyst than a simple oxide.

Product inhibition studies were carried out with an assumption that the main reaction viz. the dehydrogenation of propan-2-ol proceeds by the following steps:

The rate of dehydrogenation is not affected by diluent hydrogen over ZnCr_2O_4 (Table 3). This

TABLE 3—PRODUCT INHIBITION ON THE % FORMATION OF ACETONE OVER ZINC CHROMITE AND COBALT CHROMITE. CONTACT TIME 0.9 hr.

Catalyst	Temp. °C	Oxidised		Reduced	
		No diluent	Diluent acetone (5 mole %)	No diluent	Diluent H ₂ (9.5 ml/min)
ZnCr_2O_4	310	37	23	25	23
	340	68	45	44	42
	370	81	69	62	59
CoCr_2O_4	310	20	19	17	11
	345	33	31	24	15
	380	56	53	39	27

indicates that the desorption of hydrogen is much faster. Teichner¹⁹ and coworker have arrived at the same conclusion for ZnO . However, diluent acetone considerably retards the rate of dehydrogenation. The rate of desorption of acetone must be slower and it may be the rate controlling step.

On CoCr_2O_4 , acetone has negligible effect on the rate of reaction but hydrogen affects the reaction to a considerable extent (Table 3) and it is the desorption of hydrogen that may control the rate of the reaction.

Conclusion:

All the four catalysts used are highly selective in dehydrogenating propan-2-ol to acetone. Their dehydration ability is meagre. Copper chromite is the most effective catalyst even in the low temperature regions.

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